

IMPACT OF AEROBIC TRAINING AND YOGIC PRACTICES ON TRIGLYCERIDES AMONG OBESE COLLEGE MEN

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Abstract— This study aimed to investigate the impact of aerobic training and yogic practices on triglyceride levels among obese college men. To achieve this, 45 obese college men aged 19 to 24 years from various colleges in Sullurupeta town were randomly selected as subjects. Triglyceride levels were chosen as the dependent variable for the study. The subjects were divided into three groups: two experimental groups and one control group, each consisting of 15 subjects (n=15). Experimental Group I underwent aerobic training (ATG), Group II engaged in yogic practices (YPG), and Group III served as the control group (CG) over a training period of 12 weeks. Pre-test and post-test data on triglyceride levels were collected two days before and after the training program, respectively. Triglyceride levels were measured using the Enzymatic Colorimetric method, with fasting blood samples taken in the morning from each subject and analyzed at the Care Diagnostic Centre in Sullurupeta, India. The collected data were statistically analyzed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to determine significant improvements. When the F ratio was significant, Scheffe's test was employed as a post hoc test to identify which paired means differed significantly. The criterion for statistical significance was set at the 0.05 level of confidence ($P < 0.05$). The results indicated that systematic and well-planned aerobic training and yogic practice programs significantly reduced triglyceride levels in obese college men.

Key words — Health, Aerobic Training, Yogic Practices, Triglycerides.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aerobic training is a progressive physical conditioning program designed to stimulate cardiorespiratory activity for a sufficiently long period to produce beneficial changes in the body. This type of exercise includes activities such as running and skipping. During unsupervised sessions, physical exercise may also involve stretching, short sprints, and relaxation exercises.

While the term "aerobics" may be relatively new, the concept is not. It shares similarities with the older practice of calisthenics or physical jerks. Both involve various exercises that are not overly strenuous but, when repeated many times, result in an effective form of aerobic training. This improves both flexibility and aerobic fitness. In essence, aerobic training is a systematic approach to physical conditioning that enhances cardiorespiratory function over time.

Yoga and Pranayama can address these issues at no cost, which is why they have been integrated into modern medicine in recent decades. Yoga is an optimal lifestyle modification that aims to achieve the unity of mind, body, and spirit through asanas (exercises), pranayama, and meditation.

Breath serves as a dynamic bridge between the body and mind, and life experiences can often distort breathing patterns. Pranayama, the art of breath control and prolongation, helps bring conscious awareness to breathing, allowing individuals to reshape their habits and patterns.

2. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of aerobic training and yogic practices on triglyceride levels in obese college men. To achieve this, a qualified physician examined 150 male students enrolled in various graduation courses in Sullurupeta town, Andhra Pradesh, India, and identified 60 obese college men. From these, 45 were randomly selected as subjects, aged 19 to 24 years according to college records. The subjects were divided into three groups: two experimental groups and one control group, each consisting of 15 subjects (n=15). Experimental Group I underwent aerobic training (ATG), Group II practiced yoga (YPG), and Group III served as the control group (CG) for a 12-week training period.

All participants were informed about the nature of the study and provided their consent to participate until the end of the experiment and testing period. Both the pilot study groups and the experimental groups (ATG and YPG) received their respective training regimens independently. A qualified physician medically examined the subjects and declared them fit for the study. Participants had the option to withdraw their consent if they experienced any discomfort during the study, though there were no dropouts.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS ANALYSIS OF DATA

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for triglyceride (TG) levels, based on pre-test, post-test, and adjusted post-test data from the aerobic training (ATG), yogic practices (YPG), and control (CG) groups, is presented in Table I.

Table – I analysis of covariance for the pre test, post test and adjusted post test data on triglycerides of aerobic training, yogic practices and control groups

Tests / Groups		ATG	YPG	CG	SOV	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F ratio
Pre Test	$\bar{X}$	173.06	175.73	175.00	B	57.240	2	28.620	1.019
	σ	4.987	2.1865	7.387	W	1179.20	42	28.076	
Post Test	$\bar{X}$	169.9	174.24	177.1	B	395.734	2	197.86	7.534*
	σ	4.875	2.368	7.029	W	1103.03	42	26.263	
Adjusted Post Test	$\bar{X}$	171.4	173.2	176.8	B	223.707	2	111.85	60.037*
					W	76.386	41	1.863	

* F(0.05) (2, 42 and 2, 41) = 3.22, *Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

Table I shows that the pre-test means of triglycerides (TG) for the aerobic training (ATG), yogic practices (YPG), and control (CG) groups are 173.06, 175.73, and 175, respectively, resulting in an F ratio of 1.019. This indicates no statistically significant difference between the pre-test means at the 0.05 level of confidence. The post-test means of TG for the ATG, YPG, and CG groups are 169.9, 174.24, and 177.1, respectively, resulting in an F ratio of 7.534, which indicates a statistically significant difference between the post-test means at the 0.05 level of confidence. The adjusted post-test means for the ATG, YPG, and CG groups are 171.4, 173.2, and 176.8, respectively. The obtained F-ratio value of 60.037 is higher than the table value of 3.22 with df 2 and 41 required for significance at the 0.05 level. This indicates a significant difference among the adjusted post-test means of triglycerides (TG) for the ATG, YPG, and CG groups.

To determine which paired means had a significant difference, Scheffe’s post hoc test was applied, and the results are presented in Table II.

Table-II Scheffe’s post hoc test for differences of the adjusted post test paired means of triglycerides

Adjusted Post Test Means			Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
ATG	YPG	CG		
171.4	173.2		1.8*	1.26
171.4		176.8	5.4*	
	173.2	176.8	3.6*	

* Significant at 0.05 level

Table II shows that the adjusted post-test mean differences of TG between the groups are as follows: ATG and YPG (1.8), ATG and CG (5.4), and YPG and CG (3.6). These differences are statistically significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. It is concluded that there is a significant difference in TG levels among the groups. However, the aerobic training group (ATG) was found to be more effective in decreasing TG levels compared to the yogic practices group (YPG) and the control group (CG).

The pre-test, post-test, and adjusted post-test mean values of TG for the aerobic training group (ATG), yogic practices group (YPG), and control group (CG) are graphically presented in Figure 1.

Figure I: Line Graph Showing Pre Test, Post Test and Adjusted Post Test Means of Aerobic Training Group, Yogic Practices Group and Control group on Triglycerides

4. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The pre-test means of triglycerides (TG) for the aerobic training (ATG), yogic practices (YPG), and control (CG) groups indicate no statistically significant difference between the groups.

The post-test means of triglycerides (TG) for the three groups indicate a statistically significant difference between the groups.

The adjusted post-test means of triglycerides (TG) for the three groups also indicate a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means, with ATG and YPG performing better than CG.

It is concluded that there is a significant difference in triglycerides (TG) among the groups, with the aerobic training group (ATG) being more effective in decreasing TG levels compared to the yogic practices group (YPG) and the control group (CG).

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